

**DEPED EARLY LANGUAGE, LITERACY, AND NUMERACY PROGRAM AND ITS
RELATIONSHIP ON THE ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF LEARNERS IN
THE SELECTED ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN SOUTH LUZON: BASIS
FOR THE DEVELOPMENT FRAMEWORK FOR LITERACY, AND
NUMERACY INSTRUCTIONS FOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS**

Salve J. Hosain*, Liza Marie M. Manoos, Ph.D

¹ Concepcion National High School, SDO Quezon Province, Philippines

² Marinduque State College, Tanza, Boac, Marinduque, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: This study aimed to assess the DepEd Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy program and its relationship on the academic achievement of learners in the selected elementary schools in South Luzon basis for Development Framework for Literacy and Numeracy Instructions of Public Secondary Schools.

Research Design: A descriptive-causal comparative research design was used in this quantitative investigation to determine the extent of implementation of the DepEd Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy program in the selected elementary schools in South Luzon, the academic achievement of elementary school learners, as well as the problems and coping strategies of the teachers in addressing literacy and numeracy problems. Furthermore, a causal comparative methodology to determine the significant relation between the state of implementation of DepEd Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy programs and the academic accomplishment of learners in primary schools in South Luzon Regions was adopted.

Methodology: This study used quantitative and descriptive-correlational design. The respondents of this research were teachers who implemented ELLN and selected learners from South Luzon. The research used self-made research questionnaires and test questions to determine the learners' academic achievement which were validated by experts. Moreover, to treat the data, the research used weighted mean, Regression Analysis, and Pearson r.

Analysis: Early language programs unlock the treasure chest of words, empowering your mind to express, connect, and discover. In the world of early childhood numeracy assessment, we measure not just what children know but how they learn, explore, and explore, and play with the language of mathematics. Words in a book become more than text during early literacy assessment; they are steppingstones in a child's exploration of the universe's knowledge.

Results: The study showed that the teachers in the divisions across South Luzon adopted numeracy and literacy learning materials to improve the reading skills of learners. They also used printed learning materials for ELLN program, crafted differentiated learning materials to

address learning needs, integrated reading activities in the lesson, and joined professional organizations that will enhance their capability in teaching literacy and numeracy to improve the extent of implementation of the program in the development of macro skills and mathematical skills of learners. There was a significant relationship between the extent of implementation DepEd Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy program to the level of academic achievement of learners in the selected elementary schools in South Luzon. The study further showed that the factors affecting the reading skills of the learners as to the implementation of the ELLN program has low vocabulary words, learners poorly planned writing reports and activities, afraid of criticism, limited vocabulary, inability to interpret the material presented without graphics, and inconsistent performance of learners in solving mathematical concepts. Moreover, there is a significant relationship between listening skills, viewing skills, factors of mathematical skills, factors of reading skills, factors of writing, and listening skills. Lastly, the study revealed that the lack of learning resources to implement the ELLN program is weak on the part of teachers and learners. To address the weakness, teachers prepare interactive activities where learners can enjoy listening, reading, and writing, prepare more examples using the first language of the learners for them to understand the basic mathematical concepts, and provide a responsive reading intervention program.

Keywords: *Academic Achievement, Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy*

INTRODUCTION

As one of the president's agendas, the Basic Education Agenda stated that a child must be a reader by grade one, and the Department of Education (DepEd) is boosting its reading program through the adoption of early language literacy and numeracy. The program will improve Filipino children's literacy and numeracy skills, as well as attitudes toward lifelong learning. Its design, in particular, focuses on improving the reading and numeracy skills of kindergarten to Grade III students while adhering to the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum and providing a solid and cost-effective professional development framework for instructions. (Llego, 2023)

Literacy and numeracy are essential components of successful learning in the early grades and beyond. Numeracy is the capacity to apply mathematics and the language of numbers in everyday life. Early childhood programs draw on children's prior language, literacy, and numeracy experience at home, in their communities, and through prior engagement in early childhood programs. Language representation and mind are inextricably linked. (Tambre, 2021)

According to Ayade and colleagues (2021), the adult's role is to provide children with experiences that will improve their understanding of the purpose of literacy and numeracy in the world around them. It also defines what we need to understand about the development of literacy and numeracy in early childhood, as well as what activities should be undertaken. It aims to equip early childhood educators with the tools they need to enhance their pedagogical practice to help children develop attitudes, knowledge, and skills in these areas.

On the other hand, the COVID-19 epidemic altered everything, both inside and beyond the classroom. The educational process introduced several styles to meet the needs of all learners in the various learning modalities used in every school across the country. The implementation of new normal arose problems in terms of curriculum implementation and how to deliver hundreds of competencies in each subject in the spiral curriculum in the K to 12 programs. To make things easier, the Department of Education distilled the competencies into the most essential learning competencies (MELCS), which are tailored to the needs of students, particularly in mathematics and language subjects (Linga, 2021).

Teaching mathematics and language subjects amidst the pandemic is difficult since the basic concepts should be understood well with the assistance of the teachers. This is one of many challenges that need to be addressed by teachers to improve the learning experiences of young learners. As part of the BE-LCP implementation, the Department of Education's curriculum implementation division began chunking learning competencies to identify the most important learning competencies (MELCs). Teachers have been requested to supply learners with learning materials, and the department is prepared to distribute printed modules across the country. (Selvaraj, 2021)

Yearly, the Department of Education conducted numeracy test among the learners. Assessment in mathematics and numeracy requires more than making judgments about a student's ability. It tracks the learner's understanding of mathematical language, ideas, and abilities, as well as what they must do to succeed. Teachers desire accurate information on what each student currently knows and, with help, what the student is capable of learning. The PISA 2020 results of 19% which was a very low performance in Mathematics is very alarming. This data on the performance of the learners also affects the performance of the school as well as the teachers. In times of pandemic, teachers conducted several interventions to improve the performance of the learners in mathematics. On the other hand, interventions like the numeracy program for early grades are being implemented in this time of the pandemic. The early-grade mathematics assessment was designed and used by the teacher during the pre-pandemic period. (Magsombol, 2020)

Similarly, the literacy level of Filipino students was alarming. The perceived causes, origins, and attendant determinants of the student's reading level were non-mastery of the elements of reading, the existence of learners-at-risk, and a lack of a reading culture. The literacy level of a person can improve the quality of his or her life because it is closely tied to his or her employment. Literacy and academic achievement have a close relationship. As a result, one of the most essential purposes of today's education is to develop people with strong literacy who can grasp and challenge what they read. Individuals who are as intelligent as their classmates but have poor reading skills cannot improve as much as their contemporaries. As a result, even people with poor reading skills complete their studies. They are unable to read at the grade level expected of them, leading to anxiety and unhappiness throughout their schooling. Throughout their formal education, they are typically branded as failures. (Thomas, et al., 2021)

Among all PISA-participating countries and economies, the Philippines had a high proportion of low performers. That is, 80% of Filipino pupils did not achieve the required level of reading competency. The students' poor performance in English, Mathematics, and Science is linked to a lack of basic reading and comprehension skills. As a result, the Department of Education (DepEd) has created the Hamon: Bawat Bata Bumabasa (3Bs Initiatives) to increase reading advocacy and to commit to making every learner a reader at his or her grade level. (DepEd. gov.ph, 2022)

As a school administrator in the public secondary school in DepEd Quezon, the researcher decided to choose the research study to provide literacy as well as numeracy intervention programs among secondary learners with literacy and numeracy difficulties. This will also assess the connection between the reading comprehension and mathematical ability of secondary learners and its impact on learners' academic achievement, particularly in the selected Schools Division in Southern Luzon.

The purpose of the study is to address the gaps among elementary learners in literacy and numeracy and its impact on the academic achievement of learners in the regions.

Research Questions

This study aims to assess the DepEd Early Language, Literacy, and Numeracy program and its relationship on the academic achievement of learners in the selected elementary schools in South Luzon as the basis for a development framework for literacy and numeracy instructions of public secondary schools.

Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following subproblems:

1. What is the extent of implementation of the DepEd Early Language, Literacy, and Numeracy program in the selected elementary schools in South Luzon in terms of:
 - 1.1 Use of Recommended Early Language, Literacy, and Numeracy (ELLN) Learning Materials
 - 1.2 Nature of Learning Materials Used
 - 1.3 Teachers-Made Learning Materials
 - 1.4 Integration of Literacy and Numeracy in the Lesson
 - 1.5 Professional Development of Teachers?
2. What is the level of academic achievement of elementary school learners in DepEd Early Language, Literacy, and Numeracy Programs in terms of the following skills?
 - 2.1 Macro Skills
 - 2.1.1 Reading Skills
 - 2.1.2 Writing Skills
 - 2.1.3 Speaking Skills
 - 2.1.4 Listening Skills
 - 2.1.5 Viewing Skills
 - 2.2 Mathematical Skills
3. Is there a significant relationship of the extent of implementation DepEd Early Language, Literacy, and Numeracy program to the level of academic achievement of learners in the selected elementary schools in South Luzon in n terms of?
 - 3.1 Macro Skills
 - 3.1.1 Reading Skills
 - 3.1.2 Writing Skills
 - 3.1.3 Speaking Skills
 - 3.1.4 Listening Skills
 - 3.1.5 Viewing Skills
 - 3.2 Mathematical Skills
4. What are the factors affecting the implementation of DepEd Early Language, Literacy, and Numeracy Program on the academic achievement of learners in the selected elementary schools in South Luzon in terms of:
 - 4.1 Macro Skills
 - 4.1.1 Reading Skills
 - 4.1.2 Writing Skills
 - 4.1.3 Speaking Skills
 - 4.1.4 Listening Skills
 - 4.1.5 Viewing Skills
 - 4.2 Mathematical Skills
5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of academic achievement of learners in the selected elementary schools in South Luzon and the factors affecting the implementation of DepEd Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy program to the in terms of the following?
 - 5.1 Macro Skills

5.1.1 Reading Skills

5.1.2 Writing Skills

5.1.3 Speaking Skills

5.1.4 Listening Skills

5.1.5 Viewing Skills

5.2 Mathematics Skills

6. What are the problems encountered in the implementation of the Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy Program (ELLN) in selected elementary schools in South Luzon?

7. What coping strategies were applied by the elementary teachers in addressing the problems encountered in the implementation of the Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy Program (ELLN) in selected elementary schools in South Luzon?

8. What is the literacy and numeracy development framework for Literacy and Numeracy instruction for learners that could be proposed in the Secondary Schools in South Luzon?

METHODOLOGY

Locale: This research was conducted in South Luzon, with one school division office chosen using purposive sampling technique. Located in the Southern part of Luzon Island in the Philippines and officially designated as Region IV-A, Region IV-B and Region V, the study covered three regions, namely Region IV-A CALABARZON, Region IV-B MIMAROPA, and Region V Bicol.

Sampling Method: The purposive sampling technique was employed in this study to identify the school division (SDO) in each region across South Luzon. Stratified sampling is a sampling method that divides the whole population into smaller groups or strata to finish the sample process. The strata are formed using some common traits found in demographic data. The researcher selected the three regions as respondents to determine the extent of implementation of DepEd Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy program. More so, the researcher would like to gather more data for a more valid conclusion and to come up with a framework responsive to the needs.

Research Instrument: A self-constructed research questionnaire and test questions are the instruments employed by the researcher.

Scope and Delimitation: The purpose of this study is to analyze the DepEd Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy program and their influence on the academic accomplishment of learners in the selected elementary schools in South Luzon as the foundation for the Development Framework for Literacy and Numeracy Instructions in Public Secondary Schools. The responders are recruited from several school divisions across South Luzon. This study focused on the major influence of DepEd Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy program implementation on learner academic achievement. Furthermore, the study is limited to replies from school K to 3 teachers, ELLN District Coordinators and School Heads. The data for this study will be collected using a researcher-created questionnaire and test questions to measure the academic achievement of learners.

DISCUSSION

This study aimed to assess the DepEd Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy program and its impact to academic achievement of learners in the selected elementary schools in South Luzon basis for Development Framework for Literacy and Numeracy Instructions of Public Secondary Schools. Specifically, this study sought to determine the extent of implementation of the DepEd Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy program in the selected elementary schools in South Luzon in terms of Use of Recommended Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy (ELLN) Learning Materials, Nature of Learning Materials used, Teachers-Made Learning Materials, Integration of Literacy and Numeracy in the Lesson, and Professional Development of Teachers; the level of academic achievement of elementary school learners in DepEd Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy Program in terms of macro skills and mathematical skills; the significant impact of the extent of implementation DepEd Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy program to the level of academic achievement of learners in the selected elementary schools in South Luzon; the factors affecting the implementation of DepEd Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy Program in terms of macro skills and mathematical skills; the significant relationship between the level of academic achievement of learners in the selected elementary schools in South Luzon and the factors affecting the implementation of DepEd Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy Program.

Table 1, Significant Impact of the Extent of Implementation of DepEd ELLN Program

Independent Variables	Regression Coefficient	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Use of Recommended Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy (ELLN) Learning Materials	0.258	0.488	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Nature of Learning Materials Used	-0.427	0.500	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Teachers-Made Learning Materials	-0.074	0.899	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Integration of Literacy and Numeracy in the Lesson	-0.107	0.795	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Professional Development of Teachers	0.217	0.505	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 2. The Significant Relationship Between the Level of Academic Achievement of Learners in the Selected Elementary Schools in South Luzon and the Factors Affecting the Implementation of DepEd ELLN Program.

Indicators	Pearson Correlation	Reading			
		Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Reading Skills	0.226	Weak Positive Correlation	0.324	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Writing Skills	0.040	Weak Positive Correlation	0.864	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Speaking Skills	-0.073	Weak Negative Correlation	0.754	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Listening Skills	-0.070	Weak Negative Correlation	0.764	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Viewing Skills	-0.091	Weak Negative Correlation	0.695	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Mathematical Skills	0.080	Weak Positive Correlation	0.730	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 3

Writing Skills

Indicators	Pearson Correlation	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Reading Skills	0.140	Weak Positive Correlation	0.544	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Writing Skills	-0.063	Weak Negative Correlation	0.785	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Speaking Skills	-0.086	Weak Negative Correlation	0.711	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Listening Skills	-0.076	Weak Negative Correlation	0.745	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Viewing Skills	-0.100	Weak Negative Correlation	0.667	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Mathematical Skills	0.003	Weak Positive Correlation	0.989	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 4

Speaking Skills

Indicators	Pearson Correlation	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Reading Skills	0.086	Weak Positive Correlation	0.712	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Writing Skills	-0.199	Weak Negative Correlation	0.388	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Speaking Skills	-0.055	Weak Negative Correlation	0.813	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Listening Skills	-0.141	Weak Negative Correlation	0.542	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Viewing Skills	-0.248	Weak Negative Correlation	0.279	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Mathematical Skills	-0.062	Weak Negative Correlation	0.791	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Listening Skills

Indicators	Pearson Correlation	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Reading Skills	0.207	Weak Positive Correlation	0.368	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Writing Skills	-0.203	Weak Negative Correlation	0.922	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Speaking Skills	0.056	Weak Positive Correlation	0.811	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Listening Skills	0.102	Weak Positive Correlation	0.661	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Viewing Skills	0.020	Weak Positive Correlation	0.931	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Mathematical Skills	-0.034	Weak Negative Correlation	0.885	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 5

Viewing Skills

Indicators	Pearson Correlation	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Reading Skills	0.192	Weak Positive Correlation	0.404	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Writing Skills	-0.016	Weak Negative Correlation	0.946	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Speaking Skills	0.034	Weak Positive Correlation	0.884	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Listening Skills	0.032	Weak Positive Correlation	0.891	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Viewing Skills	-0.064	Weak Negative Correlation	0.784	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Mathematical Skills	-0.062	Weak Negative Correlation	0.790	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 6

Mathematical Skills

Indicators	Pearson Correlation	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Reading Skills	0.131	Weak Positive Correlation	0.572	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Writing Skills	-0.080	Weak Negative Correlation	0.729	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Speaking Skills	-0.034	Weak Negative Correlation	0.883	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Listening Skills	-0.099	Weak Negative Correlation	0.670	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Viewing Skills	-0.197	Weak Negative Correlation	0.393	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Mathematical Skills	-0.042	Weak Negative Correlation	0.857	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were derived:

1. The study showed that the teachers in the divisions across South Luzon adopted numeracy and literacy learning materials to improve the reading skills of learners. They also used printed learning materials for ELLN program, crafted differentiated learning materials to address learning needs, integrated reading activities in the lesson, joined professional organization that will enhance their capability in teaching literacy and numeracy to improve the extent of implementation of the program in the development of macro skills and mathematical skills of learners.
2. The study that learners can understand most of the words in the text. They are also able to identify a narrative from an informative text, confidently communicate with other students, and able to identify the kind of material they have listened to. In terms of viewing skills, learners can help summarize/discuss the material viewed while in terms of mathematical skills, ELLN program helps the learners to improve their knowledge of sets of numbers.
3. There is significant impact of the extent of implementation DepEd Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy program to the level of academic achievement of learners in the selected elementary schools in South Luzon.
4. The study showed that the factors affecting the reading skills of the learners as to the implementation of ELLN program is the low vocabulary words of the learners, learners poorly plan writing reports and activities, afraid of criticism, have limited vocabulary, cannot interpret the material presented without graphics, and inconsistent performance of learners in solving mathematical concepts.

There is a significant relationship among the listening skills, viewing skills, factors of mathematical skills, factors of reading skills, factors of writing and listening skills. Since the p-values of academic achievement in the selected elementary schools in South Luzon and the factors affecting the implementation of DepEd ELLN as to reading skills is greater than 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the level of academic achievement of learners in the selected elementary schools in South Luzon and the factors affecting the implementation of DepEd ELLN is accepted.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are hereby offered:

1. The study showed that the teachers in the divisions across South Luzon adopted numeracy and literacy learning materials to improve the reading skills of learners. Thus, it is recommended that teachers who implemented ELLN program may use adapted or self-made learning materials in the implementation of the program but make sure it will undergo content validation within the schools' district.
2. Considering the results of the study that the teachers printed learning materials for ELLN program and since there are no standardized learning materials for this program, the teachers in the division through the curriculum implementation division may craft a Division ELLN learning materials.
3. It showed that the teacher crafted literacy and numeracy learning materials and crafted differentiated learning materials to address learning needs. Thus, the school's division

may craft activities on the ELLN that will lead to the development of the macro skills and mathematical skills of the learners.

4. The findings of the study revealed that the teachers integrated reading activities in the lesson. Thus, the Department of Education, through the Bureau of Learning Delivery may conduct a national ELLN test with an end view of crafting of national ELLN learning materials.
 5. The study also showed that the teachers attended professional organization that will enhance their capability in teaching literacy and numeracy. Thus, to improve the macro skills and mathematical skills of the learners, classroom teachers are encouraged to integrate ELLN activities in the lesson.
 6. The study revealed that lack of learning resources makes the implementation of ELLN program weak in the part of teachers and learners. Thus, the Department of Education may provide enough funds in the implementation of the ELLN program.
 7. The study showed that the teachers prepare interactive activities where learners can enjoy listening reading and writing, prepare more examples using the first language of the learners for them to understand the basic mathematical concepts and provide responsive reading intervention program. Thus, the Regional Office may adapt the crafted ELLN framework of this study to bridge the gap in the macro skills and mathematical skills of Grade 7 learners.
 8. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher proposed Secondary Literacy and Numeracy (SLN) Development Framework for High School learners. Other researchers may use the results of this study in conducting related research on ELLN program, macro skills, and mathematics.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

All communications were linked to the Google connection created by the researcher. The information gathered was kept confidential and in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

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